

TRIBOLOGICAL BEHAVIOR OF A319- Al₂O₃ OR C PARTICULATE COMPOSITES FABRICATED BY STIR AND SQUEEZE CASTING METHODS

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1. General Introduction

The wear behavior of aluminum alloys has received substantial attention. In dry sliding, ductile materials such as aluminum alloys usually experience severe wear [1–5], which involves substantial surface plastic deformation at the surface. Metal-matrix composites (MMCs) have been received substantial attention from the aerospace and automotive industries because of their improved strength, high elastic modulus and increased wear resistance over conventional monolithic base alloys during the last decade. Improvements in mechanical properties and wear resistance of MMCs have already been demonstrated for a variety of reinforcements [6-14]. A319 alloy is used in transportation vehicle components in which tribological properties are important. It is well known that the wear resistance of Al–Si alloys is influenced by factors such as load and speed as well as microstructural parameters such as the morphology and volume fraction of the silicon phase [15-19]. A significant improvement in the adhesive wear resistance of Al–Si alloys reinforced with 5 wt. % Al₂O₃ particles was reported by Surappa et al. [20]. Similarly, Pramila et al. [21] noted a decrease in wear rate with increasing of SiC particle content from 15 to 20 wt.% in Al–Si alloy using a pin-on-disc apparatus[6,7]. Generally, it was found that the wear resistance of the composites was considerably higher than that of the aluminum alloy and increased with increasing Al₂O₃ particulates content and size. The majority of the wear behavior of aluminum studies has been undertaken using ferrous counterfaces. It is well known that there are strong adhesive interactions between the aluminum and ferrous materials, as shown by the substantial mechanically mixed layer that is developed in the surface of the aluminum

alloy [11,12]. The effect of 2 wt. % graphite particulate addition into Al alloy on the wear rate has been studied by Gibson et al. [22]. They have found that the wear rate of the composite material is significantly reduced by the addition of 2 wt.% graphite particulates. However, with increasing the amount of graphite content to 8 wt.%, the wear rate increases due to the low strength at the interface between graphite particulates and Al alloy. Also, because of the presence of porosity at the interface, the graphite particulates easily fracture and spall along the sliding direction with voids left on the friction surface [23-25]. It was observed that the tribological behavior of the composites in the T6 heat-treated condition is better than in the annealed condition or the unreinforced alloy. Also, it was found that AA6061-SiC MMCs showed a significant improvement in wear resistance over monolithic AA6061 alloy [26-28]. In the present study, the effect of additions of different contents of Al₂O₃ or C particulates into A319 alloy prepared by squeeze casting on the wear and friction behavior under different loads was investigated.

2. Experimental procedure

In this investigation, A319 alloy was used as matrix alloy. The chemical composition of the A319 alloy is shown in Table1. Two different types of reinforcement were used: Aluminium oxide (Al₂O₃) particulates and Graphite particulates(C). Al₂O₃ particulates (90 aktiv basisch) of size range of 63-135 µm were used as reinforcement. The particulates were supplied by MERCK Chemicals, Germany. Three weight percentages of Al₂O₃ particulates were added into A319 alloy (6.7, 13.4 and 20 wt. %), which correspond to 5, 10 and 15 vol. %, respectively. C particulates with size range of 30-50

μm were used. Two weight percentages of graphite (2.4 and 5.6 wt. %), which correspond to 3 and 7 vol. %, respectively, were added into A319 alloy. The A319 matrix composites were prepared by stir casting (vortex) followed by squeeze casting. The composites were prepared by stir casting technique (vortex technique), in which the addition of reinforcement particulates (Al_2O_3 or C) into the molten aluminum alloy was carried out by creating a vortex in the melt using a mechanical stainless steel stirrer coated with aluminite. The A319 alloy was melted in an induction furnace related to the vortex apparatus at $750\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. A jet of nitrogen gas with a suitable rate was introduced into the melt for degassing and to remove the non-metallic inclusions as well as other impurities from the melt before the addition of the reinforcements. The melt was rotated gradually by increasing the speed of the stirrer to 800 r.p.m to create a necessary vortex. The preheated particles were gradually added into the melt through the vortex. A small amount of magnesium (1% Mg), which improves the wettability between the reinforcement particles and molten Al alloy, was added along with particles, and the melt was thoroughly stirred. The stirring was continued for one minute after addition of the particles to guarantee a homogeneous distribution of the reinforcements in the matrix. Then, the molten composites were immediately poured at a pouring temperature of $680\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ into pre-heated ($350\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) rectangular cast iron moulds with $40 \times 30\text{ mm}^2$ cross section. The produced composites by vortex method were re-melted in a melting crucible furnace. The molten composite superheated to $750\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ was stirred for one min and poured into preheated tool steel die with a cylindrical cavity of an internal diameter of 50 mm, a height of 100 mm and a wall thickness of 20 mm. The die and punch temperature was set at $350\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, while the squeeze pressure was 50 MPa. After pouring the melt into the die cavity, pressurization was achieved using a 60 T hydraulic press. The holding time, that was necessary for pressurization of the melt after pouring, was 2 minutes. Dry sliding wear tests were carried out using a pin-on-disc apparatus. The composites and matrix alloy in the form of pins of 8 mm diameter and 12 mm height were allowed to slide against a rotating disc of 200 mm diameter and 3 mm thickness. The disc material was M2 high speed tool steel with hardness of 62 HRC. A portable surface roughness tester SurfTest SJ-201P was used to measure the surface roughness (Ra) of the wear test specimens and steel disc. The value of (Ra) of the

wear test specimens and steel disc before the test was 2.45 and $0.3\mu\text{m}$, respectively. The track radius was kept constant at 42 mm and the disc speed was maintained at 238 r.p.m, resulting in a constant sliding speed of 1 m/s. The applied test loads were varied between 20 and 80 N, corresponding to stress levels of 0.40 and 1.59 MPa, respectively. The sliding wear tests were carried out without interruption for 30 min. The relative humidity was 70% and initial temperature was $23\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for all the tests. The wear test runs for 0.5 hr duration. The temperature at 2 mm below the surface of the pin (using a chromel-alumel thermocouple) and friction force were recorded every five minutes. The temperature was recorded to an accuracy of $0.1\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and the friction force to an accuracy of 0.1 N. The wear losses were obtained from the difference in weight of the pin specimens measured before and after the tests using an electronic balance with sensitivity of 0.1 mg.

The worn surfaces of the pins after the wear test were examined using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). In addition, EDXA was carried out on the wear debris to determine their morphology and chemical composition.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Effect of volume fraction of particulate on the wear rate

3.1.1 Effect of volume fraction of Al_2O_3

Figure 1 shows the effect of volume fraction of Al_2O_3 particulates on wear rate of squeezed A319 based composites under a load of 80 N and sliding speed of 1 m/s. Generally, the results show that the wear rate of the composite decreases almost linearly with increasing volume fraction of Al_2O_3 particulates. A possible explanation is that as the volume fraction of the particulates increases, the contact area between the particulates and the steel disk increases, where the particulates prevent the matrix becoming directly involved in the wear process. Therefore, at high volume fraction of particulates, they cover nearly all the sample surface. Hence, the contact area is between the particulates only and steel disk. As a result of that, increasing the volume fraction of Al_2O_3 particulates in A319 based composite is accompanied by decreasing the wear rate, Fig.1. This is because Al_2O_3 particulates are ceramic materials with higher hardness and wear resistance compared with metals and alloys. Thus,

more ceramic addition leads to lower wear rate [1,15].

3.1.2 Effect of volume fraction of C

Figure 2 shows the relationship between the volume fractions of C particulates and wear rate of squeezed A319 composites at load of 80 N and sliding speed of 1 m/s. As observed in case of A319- Al_2O_3 composites, the wear rate of the composite decreases with increasing volume fraction of C particulates. Increasing the graphite contents in A319 composites is characterized by lowering the wear rate as shown in Fig.2. Graphite, a crystalline form of carbon, is sometimes considered a ceramic material although carbon is an element rather than a combination of metal and non metal atoms. Graphite has a hexagonal, layered structure [29] and it is used as a lubricant. These hexagonal layers are held together by the effect of Van der Waals bonding force. This bonding force is a secondary bond and it is weaker than the stronger covalent or ionic force. So, under the application of shear stress on the graphite structure during the wear test of the composites, the bonding is easily broken and the layers slide over each other producing the lubrication effect of the graphite, resulting in lowering the wear rate of the A319-C composites.

3.2 Effect of the applied load on the wear rate

3.2.1 A319- Al_2O_3 composites

Fig.3 shows the effect of the applied load on the wear rate of Al_2O_3 composites. The figure indicates that the effect of Al_2O_3 particulate contents on the wear rate varies with the applied load. Generally, the composites exhibit better wear resistance than the unreinforced alloy. It is clear that the matrix is the most material liable to maximum wear rate at all loads used and the wear rate decreases with increasing the Al_2O_3 particulates volume fraction at all loads. At low loads (20-40N), the differences between the wear rates of the composites are lower than that those at higher loads (60-80 N).

3.2.2 A319-C composites

The effect of the applied load on the wear rate of A319-C composites is shown in Fig 4. The figure shows that the wear rate of all the investigated materials increases with the applied load. The composites exhibit slightly better wear resistance in comparison to that of the matrix alloy. At load of 20 N, the wear rates of the composites as well as the unreinforced alloy are nearly the same. At higher load of 80 N, the wear rate of the composite is

significantly lower and the difference between the wear rates of composites is noticeable.

3.3 Effect of load and sliding distance on the coefficient of friction

3.3.1 A319- Al_2O_3 composites

Figure 5 shows the effect of applied load on the coefficient of friction (μ) of A319- Al_2O_3 composites. It can be seen that the coefficients of friction for all the tested materials increase with increasing applied load at the load range of 20–40 N. However, at load above 40 N, the coefficients of friction decrease as the load increases. Generally, it can be observed that the values of friction coefficient of A319- Al_2O_3 composites are higher than that of the matrix alloy at the same load (except at load of 80 N). This may be related to the presence of hard brittle ceramic Al_2O_3 particulate, which causes higher friction forces during wear process.

In Fig. 6, the variations of the coefficient of friction with sliding distance at load of 60 N are presented for the matrix and A319- Al_2O_3 composites. The steady-state coefficient of friction, estimated from the data of the type shown in Fig. 6, is presented in Fig. 5 as a function of the applied load. Generally, from Fig. 6, it can be seen that at the beginning of the sliding motion, the value of the coefficient of friction is lower than that at the end of the motion. A possible explanation for this is that as the wear proceeds, wear debris are generated and may adhere to the friction surfaces. Besides, the contact area of asperities of the two surfaces increases, causing an extra interaction between wear debris and friction surface. In addition, as a result of plastic deformation accompanied to friction, the amount of work hardening increases. Due to the increase in contact area and work hardening, the friction coefficient increases. In addition, the Al_2O_3 particulate or Si phase may be broken, entrapped between the composite and counterface, and therefore results in increasing the friction coefficient as the sliding distance increases.

3.3.2 A319- C composites

Figure 7 shows the relationship between the applied load and the coefficient of friction of A319-C composites. The same behavior is observed as that in case of A319- Al_2O_3 composites. It can be seen that the coefficients of friction of the composites as well as the matrix alloy increase with load at the load range of 20–40 N. However, at load above 40 N, the coefficients of friction decrease as the load increases. As expected and in contrast to the A319-

Al_2O_3 composites, the value of friction coefficient of A319- C composites at all loads is observed to be lower than the friction coefficient value of unreinforced alloy. This is due to the lubrication effect of the graphite presented in the C composites. Figure 8 shows the variations of the friction coefficient of the matrix and A319-C composites with sliding distance at load of 60 N. Generally, from Fig. 8, it can be seen that at the beginning of the sliding motion, the value of the coefficient of friction is lower than that at the end of the motion. As the wear proceeds, the contact area of asperities of the two surfaces increases, causing an extra interaction between wear debris and friction surface. This is beside the effect of plastic deformation accompanied to friction result in increment in the amount of work hardening. Due to the increase in contact area and work hardening, the friction coefficient of the composites increases, but its value is lower than that of the unreinforced alloy. This can be attributed to the lubrication effect of C particulates present in the composites.

3.4 Effect of load and sliding distance on the composite subsurface temperature

3.4.1 Effect of load on the subsurface temperature

Figure 9 shows the effect of load on the subsurface temperature of the composites after a sliding distance of 1905 m. It is seen that the temperatures of the subsurface regions increase almost linearly with the applied load. The composites reinforced with Al_2O_3 particulates exhibit higher subsurface temperatures than those of the composites reinforced with C particulates. This can be attributed to the lubrication effect of the C particulates, which results in lower coefficients of friction and subsurface temperatures in comparison to those of the A319- Al_2O_3 composites.

3.4.2 Effect of sliding distance on the subsurface temperature

Figure 10 shows subsurface temperatures at load of 60 N versus sliding distance for the matrix alloy and composites. Both the unreinforced alloy and composites show a continuous increase in temperature with the sliding distance. The rate of increase in temperature is higher for the composites than for the unreinforced alloy. As mentioned above, the wear proceeds, the contact area of asperities of the two surfaces increases, causing an extra interaction between wear debris and friction surface. Due to the increase in contact area and the presence

of the wear debris between the two surfaces, the friction force increases, as a result, the contact surface temperatures increase as the sliding distance increases [30].

3.5 Morphology of the worn surfaces and wear debris

3.5.1 A319- Al_2O_3 composites

The worn surfaces of the composite pins were examined under SEM to investigate the wear mechanisms [31]. SEM photograph of the A319 alloy and its composites tested at a load of 20 and 80 N is presented in Figs. 11 and 14 respectively. For the A319 alloy, the presence of grooves along the sliding direction and the formation of extensive lips along the groove walls point out to extensive plasticity. The larger groove width at the test load of 80 N compared to the grooves formed at 20 N was also observed, Fig.14. Since the matrix/particulate interfacial area increases as the size of the particulates decreases, large particulates are expected to remain embedded longer than smaller particulates until the matrix can no longer support them or until they are broken down into smaller pieces. Hence, for the composites based on large particulate, these large particulates very effectively resist the deformation and are not easily extracted by the steel disc because of their large size, high values of hardness and good bonding with the matrix. The large particulates protruding from the surface of the composite bear most of the wear load and the surface hardness of the composite are mainly a result of the hardness of the particulates. The wear debris generated at load 20 N from the composite are in the form of chips and fine particulates, Fig. 12. The composition of the debris was determined through EDX studies. The debris is observed to consist mainly of Al, Si, Cu, O and Fe, Fig. 13. These results clearly indicate that the debris generated during wear at low loads is a mechanical mixture of particles detached from both the specimen and the counterface. At load of 80 N Fig.14, the worn surfaces of the composites as well as the matrix alloy are characterized by severe plastic deformation and damage in the form of cavitations. The evidence of adhesive wear is found in the form of adhesive ploughing of the surface. During wear process, the wear of material depends primarily upon nucleation and propagation of cracks on the surface and subsurface regions. In general, the available site for crack nucleation in Al-Si alloy is the Al/Si interface. In the initial stage of wear process, silicon particle resists against destructive action and protects the

surface. During wear process, these cracks are propagated and later joined together to form flake-shaped wear debris. Additionally, the hard silicon particles tend to fragment into small pieces and separated out from the matrix. The fragmentation of silicon particles takes place when the stress applied on the Si particle is more than the fracture strength of silicon [30]. The view of the wear patches shown in Fig. 14(b, d) clearly reveals that a layer of material has been removed as debris from these areas and that the debris is in the form of thin sheets. Also, the worn surfaces of the composites are characterized by the formation of numerous grooves. Numerous short cracks more or less perpendicular to the sliding direction can be observed, Fig. 14(b,d). These cracks probably have originated from the beneath the wear surface and propagated to the free surface. This implies that plastic deformation is localized in the subsurface region of the material adjacent to the contact surfaces. The deformation induced by shear results in the generation of large strain in the subsurface layer. Large strain localization in the subsurface layer leads to the crack initiation and propagation through the shear bands. It has been reported that the wear damage is mainly localized near the subsurface region and that it is originated at the particulates. Large plastic strains generally enhance the nucleation and growth of the voids at the particulates located in the subsurface region. These voids then grow and coalesce to form crack, alloying the wear debris to delaminate [32]. Figure 15 (a-c) shows SEM of the wear debris of the A319- Al₂O₃ composites tested at load of 80 N, the wear debris consists of Al, Si, Cu, O and Fe, Fig 16. This indicates that the debris formation mechanisms include subsurface delamination and abrasion. Presence of Fe in the debris can be taken as an indication of abrasion action of the exposed tips of Al₂O₃ particulates and Si at the worn surface on the steel counterface. The broken fragments of the Al₂O₃ particulates, which mixed in the loose debris, may have acted as third body abrasive on both composite and steel surface [30].

3.5.2 A319-C composites

Figure 11(c) and Fig. 14(c) show the SEM of the A319-C composites at loads of 20 and 80 N, respectively. The difference in the appearance of the worn surfaces is clear between the plastic deformation in higher and lower loads. But, the size of the wear debris of A319- Al₂O₃ composite the as well as the A319-C composites are relatively smaller

as compared with that of unreinforced alloy debris. Fig. 12(c) and Fig.15(c). The smaller size of the A319-C debris may be attributed to the lubrication effect of the graphite particle rather than the effect of harder Al₂O₃ particulates in the composite reinforced with Al₂O₃ particulates. In wear of A319-C composites, the graphite displays a very low coefficient of friction ranging from 0.1 to 0.2, while sliding on another surface; thus, it can act as a solid lubricant. In case of Al-C composites, when the composite pin is subjected to deformation during sliding, there is a plastic flow of the metal at the surface layer that tends to cover the C particulates, restricting their transfer to the counterface until the metallic layer covering the C particulates wear away. Then, the applied load crushes the C particulates into fine particulates and spreads them on the sliding surface. During the sliding, the crushed particulates are spread over the composite pin surface, sheared and joined to form a continuous C layer (film of solid lubricant). During this period, the solid lubricant comes out from the crushed C particulates and as wear proceeds, spread over the sliding surface of the composite pin and transfer to the counterface. This process maintains a continuous supply of graphite, which acts as a solid lubricant between two sliding surfaces. In other words, the composite becomes self-lubricating because of the transfer of the Crushed C particulates to the tribosurfaces and their formation into a thin film. Therefore, the improvement in the wear behavior of the composite can be attributed to the ability of the graphite to come out of their embedded state in the matrix and spread evenly in the form of a solid lubricating film over the tribological surface to provide lubrication [30].

4. Equations

The wear rate [R (mm³/m)] was calculated using the formula [7]:

$$R = \Delta W / (d \times \rho)$$

Where ΔW is weight loss, d is sliding distance and ρ is the density.

5. Conclusions

1. A319 alloy reinforced with Al₂O₃ or C exhibits a superior wear resistance in comparison to that of the unreinforced alloy.
2. The contact surface temperatures increase with increasing the applied load for all the tested materials during the wear test.
3. The coefficients of friction of A319- Al₂O₃ composites are higher than those of the A319 alloy, while the coefficients of friction of A319- C composites are lower than those of the A319 alloy.
4. The wear rates of A319 reinforced with Al₂O₃ or C particulates are decreased with increasing the particulate content.

6. References

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Tables, Diagrams and Figures

Table 1 Chemical composition of the A319 alloy (wt. %)

Si	Cu	Fe	Zn	Mn	Ni	Cr	Pb	Sn	V	Al
5.73	3.87	0.209	0.068	0.009	0.006	0.001	0.07	0.066	0.006	rest

Fig. 1 Wear rate of A319-Al₂O₃ composite as a function of particulate volume fraction

Fig.2 Wear rate of A319-C composite as a function of particulate volume fraction

Fig. 3 Effect of the applied load on the wear rate of A319-Al₂O₃ composites

Fig. 4 Effect of the applied load on the wear rate of A319-C composites

Fig. 7 Effect of load on the coefficient of friction of A319-C composites

Fig. 5 Effect of load on the coefficient of friction (μ) of A319- Al₂O₃ composites

Fig. 8 Effect of sliding distance on the coefficient of friction (μ) of C-composites

Fig. 6 Variations of the coefficient of friction of A319-Al₂O₃ composites with sliding distance

Fig. 9 Effect of load on the subsurface temperature of the composites

Fig.10 Variation of composite pin subsurface temperature with sliding distance for matrix alloy and composites (test load: 60 N).

Fig. 11 SEM micrographs of the worn surfaces of the A319 alloy and composites tested at 20 N

Fig. 12 SEM micrographs of the wear debris from the A319 alloy and composites tested at 20 N

Fig. 13 EDXA of the worn debris of the A319 alloy and its composites tested at 20 N

Fig. 14 SEM micrographs of the worn surfaces of the A319 alloy and its composites tested at 80 N

Fig. 15 SEM morphology of the wear debris from the A319 alloy and its composites tested at 80 N

Fig.16 EDXA of the worn debris of the A319 alloy and its composites tested 80 N